

CoeusAI SOFTWARE MANAGEMENT PLAN

20250225, Produced by Maurice de Kleijn and Jitte Waagen, based on the input and discussion in the Lorentz Workshop Intelligent & Fuzzy: Machine Learning for Anomaly Detection:

<https://www.lorentzcenter.nl/intelligent-en-fuzzy-machine-learning-for-anomaly-detection.html>

Purpose

- **What problem does it solve?**

Fast identification of [archaeological] anomalies in multiband geospatial remote sensing data

- **Who is the intended audience?**

Everyone working with that type of data

- **What are its advantages and limitations?**

Fast identification of [archaeological] anomalies in multiband geospatial remote sensing data

Fast and effective, but focused [limited] at geospatial data

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User documentation

Front-end:

- **Tutorial** (video, markdown – first markdown later video) with real data (i.e. aerial photographs, multispectral, LiDAR, Thermal etc.)
- **Tooltips**
- **Methods** (explanation | readme)
- Add a section with potential other applications (e.g. medical sciences/ paintings)

Backend:

- **Jupyter notebook (tutorial)**
- **MkDocs with user documentation**

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Deployment Documentation

- QGIS PLUGIN METADATA for <http://plugins.qgis.org>

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Developer Documentat -ion

- Available through Github

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Repository

- The tool will become available through:
- GITHUB (**VERSION CONTROL (see below)** is exclusively done through GitHub)
- Code is owned by NLeSc and 4D Research Lab UvA

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Software licensing and compatibility

- By default Apache 2.0 (Netherlands eScience Center)
- QGIS requires GPL2+ (but we can also decide to not put it in QGIS plugin library <https://plugins.qgis.org>)
- Dependencies form a potential issue

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Citation

- Citation File Format (CFF in GitHub repo)
- Zenodo for DOI (minter)
- Research Software Directory (<https://research-software-directory.org/>)
- QGIS plugin library (<https://plugins.qgis.org>)

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Maintenance

POST PROJECT [EXTERNAL] CONTRIBUTORS:

- [external] Contributions by users done via GitHub in the form of issues (or email)

- Pull requests procedure with approval from peers (maintainers i.e. Ou Ku o.ku@esciencecenter.nl / Christiaan Meijer, NLeSc later to be replaced by someone else if tool runs wild)

GOVERNANCE MODEL:

- 4DResearch lab is constant factor, thus main responsibility lies with them (at least for porting info)
- Project ends in Summer 2025
- Invite Lorentz center workshop participants every ½ year
- Possibly open [virtual] office hour for external users/ contributors
- User testing before every release

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- No user adoption
- Competing tools
- Maintenance is initially tackled by governance (although relatively weak at the moment, if tool has a lot of users more complex structure is required)
- GitHub is Microsoft, in theory it is possible that US blocks EU users, however that is on such a high level, that EU will probably have a solution
- CoeusAI (and/or dependencies) are not compatible with latest QGIS LTR

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- During project Netherlands eScience Center after the project 4D research lab as point of contact

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- Done in Github

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Testing

- Users testing before every release (possibly in experiment?)
- As done in context of Lorentz workshop
- Asynchronous testing by users (results as issues; if any)
- **Autotesting (as part of GitHub Workflow)**
- **Decided to only go for QGIS LTR = every year**
[\(https://qgis.org/resources/roadmap/\)](https://qgis.org/resources/roadmap/)

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Packaging

- PiPy / Conda (once packaged)
- QGIS PLUGIN

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Software Engineering Quality

- Various levels/ methods to ensure / assess the quality
 - How fair is NLeSc tooling
 - Unit testing (see testing above)
 - Rough/Black (which we are not doing, might be overkill in this case)
 - Formatters and Linters (to align indentation and reformat functions etc.)
 - Next level would be SonarQube
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